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Bridgehead Nitrogen Heterocycles : Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of a Few Heterocycles derived from 6-Chloro-5H-2,3-dihydro-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-b]indole-3-thione

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In continuation of our earlier studies¹ on the orientation of cyclisation in the reaction of unsymmetrical mercaptoazoles with bifunctional compounds, we report herein the results of our study on the reaction of unsymmetrical azine (mercaptoindolotriazine) with alkylhalides and 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline.

Condensation of 6-chloro-5H-2,3-dihydro-1,2,4-triazino[5,6-b]indole-3-thione (2), obtained by the

reaction of 7-chloroisatin with thiosemicarbazide followed by the cyclisation of the intermediate 7-chloroisatin-3-thiosemicarbazone (1) with alkali, with 1,2-dibromoethane was likely to give 9-chloro-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[3',2':2,3][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole (3) or 6-chloro-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[2',3':3,4]-[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole (6) or both depending on the mode of cyclisation. However, the reaction of 2 with 1,2-dibromoethane gave a single product (tlc) to which the structure 3 and not 6 was assigned, as the product was not identical with an authentic sample of 6 obtained by the reaction of 1 with 1,2-dibromoethane (Scheme 1).

The amide carbonyl ($-NH-C=O$) absorption 1695 cm^{-1} in 1, was found absent in the ir spectrum of the product obtained by the reaction of 1 with 1,2-dibromoethane. This corroborated the cyclic structure of 6. The structures 3 and 6 were further supported by their pmr spectral data.

Similarly, the condensation of 2 with 1,3-dibromopropane and 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline yielded 10-chloro-4H-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazino[3',2':2,3][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole (4) and 11-chloroquinoxalino[2',3':4,5]thiazolo[3,2-b]indolo[2,3-e][1,2,4]triazine (5) respectively as they were not found to be identical with their authentic angular isomers 7 and 8 obtained from 1 by similar treatment with 1,3-dibromopropane and 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline respectively.

Scheme 1. Reagents : (i) KOH, (ii) BrCH₂CH₂Br, (iii) BrCH₂CH₂CH₂Br, (iv) 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline, NaOAc.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Tlc was performed on silica-gel plates using acetone-benzene (1 : 3) as irrigant. Ir and pmr spectra were recorded on Beckman IR-20 and Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) instruments; chemical shifts downfield from TMS.

7-Chloroisatin-3-thiosemicarbazone (1): A mixture containing boiling solution of 7-chloroisatin (9.0 g, 0.05 mol) in acetic acid (80 ml) and thiosemicarbazide (5.0 g, 0.55 mol) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed on a heating mantle for 0.5 h. The resulting brown coloured solid was washed with water and crystallised from DMF-ethanol furnishing dark yellow crystals (5 g, 50%), m.p. 245° (Found: N, 22.16; S, 12.83. $C_9H_7N_4OSCl$ requires: N, 22.00; S, 12.57%); ν_{max} 770 (1,2,3-trisubstituted-benzene), 1 145 (C=S), 1 610 (C=N), 1 695 (C=O), 3 140, 3 350 and 3 458 cm^{-1} (NH, NH₂).

6-Chloro-5H-2,3-dihydro[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole-3-thione (2): 7-Chloroisatin-3-thiosemicarbazone (1; 7.62 g, 0.03 mol) in 4% KOH (200 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the insoluble material was removed by filtration. The filtrate on neutralisation with dilute hydrochloric acid gave a yellow solid which was washed well with water and crystallised from DMF-H₂O mixture to furnish light yellow crystals (6 g, 84.7%), m.p. 235° (Found: N, 23.38; S, 13.92. $C_9H_5N_4SCl$ requires: N, 23.68; S, 13.53%); ν_{max} 775 (1,2,3-trisubstituted-benzene ring), 1 140 (C=S), 1 572 (C=N), 1 620 (C=N) and 3 300 cm^{-1} (NH).

9-Chloro-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[3',2':2,3][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole hydrobromide (3): A mixture of 2 (1.18 g, 0.005 mol) and 1,2-dibromoethane (0.94 g, 0.005 mol) in a mixture of DMF (20 ml) and absolute alcohol (20 ml) was refluxed on a heating mantle for 4 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured into water and the solid thus obtained was crystallised from methanol as orange flakes (0.9 g, 53%), m.p. 226° (Found: C, 38.09; H, 2.62; N, 15.90; S, 9.58. $C_{11}H_8N_4S_2ClBr$ requires: C, 38.43; H, 2.33; N, 16.30; S, 9.32%); ν_{max} 3 200 (NH), 1 610 (C=N), 780 (1,2,3-trisubstituted-benzene ring); δ (TFA) 3.38 (2H, t, SCH₂), 4.10 (2H, t, NCH₂), 5.28 (1H, bs, NH), 7.30–8.50 (3H, m, C₆-H, C₇-H and C₈-H).

10-Chloro-4H-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazino[3',2':2,3][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole hydrobromide (4): Condensation of 2 (1.18 g, 0.005 mol) with 1,3-dibromopropane (1.01 g, 0.005 mol) in mixture of DMF (20 ml) and absolute alcohol (20 ml), following the above procedure furnished 4 as orange coloured crystals (1.2 g, 67%), m.p. > 250° (Found: C, 40.62; H, 2.51; N, 15.98; S, 9.40. $C_{12}H_{10}N_4S_2ClBr$ requires: C, 40.28; H, 2.80; N, 15.66; S, 8.95%); ν_{max} 3 170 (NH), 1 600 (C=N) and 770 cm^{-1} (1,2,3-trisubstituted-benzene ring).

11-Chloroquinoxalino[2',3':4,5]thiazolo[3,2-b]indolo[2,3-e][1,2,4]triazine (5): A mixture of 2

(1.18 g, 0.005 mol), 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline (0.995 g, 0.005 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.82 g, 0.01 mol) in a mixture of DMF (20 ml) and absolute alcohol (20 ml) was refluxed for 4 h, then cooled and poured into water. The resulting brown solid was washed with water and crystallised from methanol as red coloured crystals (0.8 g, 44%), m.p. 222° (Found: C, 56.72; H, 2.08; N, 23.54; S, 8.49. $C_{17}H_7N_6S_2Cl$ requires: C, 56.28; H, 1.93; N, 23.17; S, 8.83%); ν_{max} 1 600, 1 580 (C=N), 750 and 770 cm^{-1} (1,2-disubstituted and 1,2,3-trisubstituted benzene rings).

6-Chloro-2,3-dihydrothiazolo[2',3':3,4][1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole hydrobromide (6): A mixture of 1 (1.27 g, 0.005 mol) and 1,2-dibromoethane (0.94 g, 0.005 mol) in a mixture of anhydrous ethanol (20 ml) and DMF (20 ml) was refluxed on a heating mantle for 4 h, then cooled and poured into water. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from methanol giving brown coloured granular crystals (0.8 g, 47%), m.p. > 250° (Found: C, 38.68; H, 2.12; N 15.94; S, 9.80. $C_{11}H_8N_4S_2ClBr$ requires: C, 38.43; H, 2.33; N, 16.30; S, 9.32%); ν_{max} 3 200, 3 140 (NH), 1 620 (C=N) and 785 cm^{-1} (1,2,3-trisubstituted benzene ring); δ (TFA) 3.40 (2H, t, SCH₂), 3.98 (2H, t, NCH₂) and 7.50–8.50 (3H, m, C₇-H, C₈-H and C₉-H).

10-Chloro-1H-2,3-dihydro[1,3]thiazino[2',3':3,4]-[1,2,4]triazino[5,6-b]indole hydrobromide (7): Condensation of 1 (1.27 g, 0.005 mol) and 1,3-dibromopropane (1.01 g, 0.005 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (20 ml) and DMF (20 ml) following the above procedure yielded brown coloured crystals (methanol) (1.0 g, 56%), m.p. > 250° (Found: C, 39.38; H, 3.23; N, 15.85; S, 9.28. $C_{12}H_{10}N_4S_2ClBr$ requires: C, 40.28; H, 2.80; N, 15.66; S, 8.95%); ν_{max} 3 210, 3 125 (NH), 1 600 (C=N) and 780 cm^{-1} (1,2,3-trisubstituted-benzene ring).

1-Chloroquinoxalino[2',3':4,5]thiazolo[2,3-c]indolo[2,3-e][1,2,4]triazine (8): A mixture of 1 (1.27 g, 0.005 mol), 2,3-dichloroquinoxaline (0.995 g, 0.005 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.82 g, 0.01 mol) in anhydrous ethanol (20 ml) and DMF (20 ml) was refluxed on a heating mantle for 4 h, then cooled and poured into water. The resulting red solid was washed thoroughly with water and crystallised from methanol giving red crystals (0.8 g, 44%), m.p. > 250° (Found: C, 56.60; H, 1.98; N, 23.44; S, 8.52. $C_{17}H_7N_6S_2Cl$ requires: C, 56.28; H, 1.93; N, 23.17; S, 8.83%); ν_{max} 1 600, 1 580 (C=N), 770 and 760 (1,2,4-irsubstituted and o-disubstituted benzene ring).

Antimicrobial activity: Compounds 3–8 were evaluated for their antibacterial activity against the gram-positive, *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram-negative, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and for their antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* by neat samples and serial plate dilution method².

Compounds 3–7 exhibited activity against *S. aureus* and *C. albicans*, when treated as neat samples

and may be used for local application in the form of powder or ointment provided further studies indicate absence of toxicity following local application.

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Further Chemical Investigation of

Murraya exotica

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PREVIOUSLY we reported the structure of several coumarins, flavones and cinnamic acid derivatives from *Murraya exotica*¹⁻³. Further chemical investigation reveals the presence of another coumarin (1) from the leaves of *M. exotica*.

Dried and powdered leaves of *M. exotica* (1.5 kg) was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) in a soxhlet for 36 h. The solvent was then concentrated and chromatographed over silica gel. Compound 1 was isolated from the chloroform eluate as light yellow crystalline solid, C₁₅H₁₄O₄ (M⁺ 258), m.p. 135–37°; [α]_D²⁵CHCl₃ = ±0°; soluble in alkali giving a yellow solution from which it could be regenerated by acidification indicating the presence of a δ-lactone; λ_{max} 323, 236 and 214 nm (characteristic of 7-oxygenated coumarin)⁴; ν_{max}(KBr) 1740–1725br (C=O), 1660, 1618 and 1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic); δ (300 MHz; CDCl₃) 10.15 (1H, s, CHO), 7.57 (1H, d, J 9.5Hz, C-4), 6.13 (1H, d, J 9.5Hz, C-3), 7.37 (1H, d, J 8.6Hz, C-5), 6.82 (1H, d, J 8.6Hz, C-6), 3.75 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.36 (3H, s, C-2'-CH₃) and 1.71 (3H, s, C-2'-CH₃).

The physical data of the compound was found to be identical with Murralongin which was previously assigned as 2 by Talapatra *et al.*⁵ and revised recently by Imani *et al.*⁶ as 1 by X-ray crystallography. Our analysis of ¹³C nmr spectral data of the compound corroborates the revised structure 1 of the molecule.

The data presented below exhibit that the observed chemical shifts of the two olefinic carbons of the isoprenyl side chain of murralongin are in better agreement with the values calculated⁷ for these two carbons of the structure 1 than those of 2. The chemical shifts assigned to different carbons are shown around 1.

Ph	1'	2'	CH ₃	Ph	1'	2'	CH ₃	Ph	1'	2'	CH ₃
	C	=	C		C	=	C		C	=	C
	H ₃ C		CHO		H ₃ C		CHO		H ₃ C		CHO
	Calo. (δ)				Observed (δ)				Calo. (δ)		
	C-1', 151.20				129.10				198.10		
	C-2', 188.10				152.55				146.20		

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